

OPR-2025-00276

Details

Working Title NOS Mapping and Surveying draft PEIS Reinitiation

Request Received Jan 10, 2025

Region OPR

Division ESA Interagency Cooperation Division

Branch N/A

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
Survey	Geophysical

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Commerce (DOC) - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Ocean Service (NOS)

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Coral	Boulder Star Coral	<i>Orbicella franksi</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Staghorn Coral	<i>Acropora cervicornis</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Rough Cactus Coral	<i>Mycetophyllia ferox</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Pillar Coral	<i>Dendrogyra cylindrus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened, Proposed Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Mountainous Star Coral	<i>Orbicella faveolata</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Lobed Star Coral	<i>Orbicella annularis</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Elkhorn Coral	<i>Acropora palmata</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Seriatopora aculeata</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✓
Coral	Coral	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradvivisa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora jacquelineae</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Dolphin	Killer Whale	<i>Orcinus orca</i>	Southern Resident DPS	Endangered Southern Resident DPS	✓	✗
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Endangered Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	✓	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Fish	Sockeye Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus nerka</i>	Snake River ESU	Endangered <i>Snake River ESU</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Sockeye Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus nerka</i>	Ozette Lake ESU	Threatened <i>Ozette Lake ESU</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Smalltooth Sawfish	<i>Pristis pectinata</i>	U.S. portion of range DPS	Endangered <i>U.S. portion of range DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Shortnose Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser brevirostrum</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Indo-West Pacific DPS	Threatened <i>Indo-West Pacific DPS</i>	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Eastern Pacific DPS	Endangered <i>Eastern Pacific DPS</i>	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Central and Southwest Atlantic DPS	Threatened <i>Central and Southwest Atlantic DPS</i>	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Fish	Nassau Grouper	<i>Epinephelus striatus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened <i>Range-wide</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Gulf Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus desotoi</i>	Range-wide	Threatened <i>Range-wide</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	California Central Valley DPS	Threatened <i>California Central Valley DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Central California Coast DPS	Threatened <i>Central California Coast DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Yelloweye Rockfish	<i>Sebastes rubberimus</i>	Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS	Threatened <i>Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Upper Willamette River DPS	Threatened <i>Upper Willamette River DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Upper Columbia River DPS	Threatened <i>Upper Columbia River DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Southern California DPS	Endangered <i>Southern California DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	South-Central California Coast DPS	Threatened <i>South-Central California Coast DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Snake River Basin DPS	Threatened <i>Snake River Basin DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Puget Sound DPS	Threatened <i>Puget Sound DPS</i>	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Northern California DPS	Threatened <i>Northern</i>	✓	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Middle Columbia River DPS	Threatened Middle California DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Lower Columbia River DPS	Threatened Lower Columbia River DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Green Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser medirostris</i>	Southern DPS	Threatened Southern DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Eulachon	<i>Thaleichthys pacificus</i>	Southern DPS	Threatened Southern DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Lower Columbia River ESU	Threatened Lower Columbia River ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Central Valley Spring-Run ESU	Threatened Central Valley Spring-Run ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	California Coastal ESU	Threatened California Coastal ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Bocaccio	<i>Sebastes paucispinis</i>	Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS	Endangered Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	South Atlantic DPS	Endangered South Atlantic DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	New York Bight DPS	Endangered New York Bight DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Gulf of Maine DPS	Threatened Gulf of Maine DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Chesapeake Bay DPS	Endangered Chesapeake Bay DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Carolina DPS	Endangered Carolina DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Atlantic Salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Gulf of Maine DPS	Endangered Gulf of Maine DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Puget Sound ESU	Threatened Puget Sound ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Sacramento River Winter-Run ESU	Endangered Sacramento River Winter- Run ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Southern Oregon and Northern California Coasts ESU	Threatened Southern Oregon and Northern California Coasts ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Oregon Coast ESU	Threatened Oregon Coast ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Lower Columbia River ESU	Threatened Lower	✓	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Lower Columbia River ESU	Columbia River ESU	✓	~
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Central California Coast ESU	Endangered Central	✓	✗
Fish	Chum Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>	Hood Canal Summer-Run ESU	Threatened Hood Canal Summer-Run ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chum Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>	Columbia River ESU	Threatened Columbia River ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Upper Willamette River ESU	Threatened Upper Willamette River ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Upper Columbia River Spring-Run ESU	Endangered Upper Columbia River Spring-Run ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Snake River Spring/Summer Run ESU	Threatened Snake River Spring/Summer Run ESU	✓	✗
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Snake River Fall-Run ESU	Threatened Snake River Fall-Run ESU	✓	✗
Mollusk	Queen Conch	<i>Alger gigas</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	White Abalone	<i>Haliotis sorenseni</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	Black Abalone	<i>Haliotis cracherodii</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Pinniped	Steller Sea Lion	<i>Eumetopias jubatus</i>	Western DPS	Endangered Western DPS	✓	✗
Pinniped	Ringed Seal	<i>Phoca hispida hispida</i>	Arctic subspecies	Threatened Arctic subspecies	✓	✗
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Pinniped	Guadalupe Fur Seal	<i>Arctocephalus townsendi</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Pinniped	Bearded Seal	<i>Erignathus barbatus</i>	Beringia DPS	Threatened Beringia DPS	✓	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central West Pacific DPS	Endangered Central West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	Mexico's Pacific Coast Breeding Colonies	Endangered Mexico's Pacific Coast Breeding Colonies	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened All Other Areas	✗	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Northwest Atlantic Ocean DPS	Threatened Northwest Atlantic Ocean DPS	✓	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	North Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered North Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Range-wide	Endangered	✓	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Kemp's Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Mediterranean DPS	Endangered Mediterranean DPS	✗	✓
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	East Pacific DPS	Threatened East Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central South Pacific DPS	Endangered Central South Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central North Pacific DPS	Threatened Central North Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Whale	North Pacific Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena japonica</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Rice's Whale	<i>Balaenoptera ricei</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	North Atlantic Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena glacialis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Western North Pacific DPS	Endangered Western North Pacific DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Mexico DPS	Threatened Mexico DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Central America DPS	Endangered Central America DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Bowhead Whale	<i>Balaena mysticetus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Beluga Whale	<i>Delphinapterus leucas</i>	Cook Inlet DPS	Endangered Cook Inlet DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗

Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Coral	Elkhorn Coral	<i>Acropora palmata</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Rough Cactus Coral	<i>Mycetophyllia ferox</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Pillar Coral	<i>Dendrogyra cylindrus</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Seriatopora aculeata	<i>Seriatopora aculeata</i>	Range-wide	Proposed ⓘ Range-wide
Coral	Mountainous Star Coral	<i>Orbicella faveolata</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Lobed Star Coral	<i>Orbicella annularis</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide

Coral	Isopora crateriformis	<i>Isopora crateriformis</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Coral	Acropora speciosa	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Acropora retusa	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Acropora jacquelineae	<i>Acropora jacquelineae</i>	Range-wide	Proposed ⓘ Range-wide
Coral	Staghorn Coral	<i>Acropora cervicornis</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Acropora globiceps	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Boulder Star Coral	<i>Orbicella franksi</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Designated Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS
Dolphin	Killer Whale	<i>Orcinus orca</i>	Southern Resident DPS	Designated Southern Resident DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Central California Coast DPS	Designated Central California Coast DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	California Central Valley DPS	Designated California Central Valley DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Lower Columbia River DPS	Designated Lower Columbia River DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Middle Columbia River DPS	Designated Middle Columbia River DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Northern California DPS	Designated Northern California DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Puget Sound DPS	Designated Puget Sound DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Snake River Basin DPS	Designated Snake River Basin DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	South-Central California Coast DPS	Designated South-Central California Coast DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Southern California DPS	Designated Southern California DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Upper Columbia River DPS	Designated Upper Columbia River DPS
Fish	Steelhead Trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Upper Willamette River DPS	Designated Upper Willamette River DPS
Fish	Yelloweye Rockfish	<i>Sebastes rubberimus</i>	Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS	Designated Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS
Fish	Nassau Grouper	<i>Epinephelus striatus</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	South Atlantic DPS	Designated South Atlantic DPS
Fish	Sockeye Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus nerka</i>	Snake River ESU	Designated Snake River ESU
Fish	Sockeye Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus nerka</i>	Ozette Lake ESU	Designated Ozette Lake ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Snake River Spring/Summer Run ESU	Designated Snake River Spring/Summer Run ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Snake River Fall-Run ESU	Designated Snake River Fall-Run ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Sacramento River Winter-Run ESU	Designated Sacramento River Winter-Run ESU

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Puget Sound ESU	Designated Puget Sound ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Lower Columbia River ESU	Designated Lower Columbia River ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Central Valley Spring-Run ESU	Designated Central Valley Spring-Run ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	California Coastal ESU	Designated California Coastal ESU
Fish	Bocaccio	<i>Sebastes paucispinis</i>	Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS	Designated Puget Sound/Georgia Basin DPS
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	New York Bight DPS	Designated New York Bight DPS
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Gulf of Maine DPS	Designated Gulf of Maine DPS
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Chesapeake DPS	Designated Chesapeake DPS
Fish	Atlantic Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus</i>	Carolina DPS	Designated Carolina DPS
Fish	Atlantic Salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Gulf of Maine DPS	Designated Gulf of Maine DPS
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Central California Coast ESU	Designated Central California Coast ESU
Fish	Chum Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>	Hood Canal Summer-Run ESU	Designated Hood Canal Summer-Run ESU
Fish	Chum Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>	Columbia River ESU	Designated Columbia River ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Upper Willamette River ESU	Designated Upper Willamette River ESU
Fish	Chinook Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Upper Columbia River Spring-Run ESU	Designated Upper Columbia River Spring-Run ESU
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Oregon Coast ESU	Designated Oregon Coast ESU
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Southern Oregon and Northern California Coasts ESU	Designated Southern Oregon and Northern California Coasts ESU
Fish	Eulachon	<i>Thaleichthys pacificus</i>	Southern DPS	Designated Southern DPS
Fish	Green Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser medirostris</i>	Southern DPS	Designated Southern DPS
Fish	Gulf Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser oxyrinchus desotoi</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Fish	Smalltooth Sawfish	<i>Pristis pectinata</i>	U.S. portion of range DPS	Designated U.S. portion of range DPS
Fish	Coho Salmon	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Lower Columbia River ESU	Designated Lower Columbia River ESU
Mollusk	Black Abalone	<i>Haliotis cracherodii</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Pinniped	Bearded Seal	<i>Erignathus barbatus</i>	Beringia DPS	Designated Beringia DPS
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Pinniped	Ringed Seal	<i>Phoca hispida hispida</i>	Arctic subspecies	Designated Arctic subspecies
Pinniped	Steller Sea Lion	<i>Eumetopias jubatus</i>	Western DPS	Designated Western DPS
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Northwest Atlantic Ocean DPS	Designated Northwest Atlantic Ocean DPS
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide

Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Central America DPS	Designated <i>Central America DPS</i>
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Western North Pacific DPS	Designated <i>Western North Pacific DPS</i>
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Mexico DPS	Designated <i>Mexico DPS</i>
Whale	North Atlantic Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena glacialis</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Whale	North Pacific Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena japonica</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Whale	Beluga Whale	<i>Delphinapterus leucas</i>	Cook Inlet DPS	Designated <i>Cook Inlet DPS</i>

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
United States		Federal Waters		Gulf of America (US Waters)		
United States		Federal Waters		North Atlantic Ocean		
United States		Federal Waters		North Pacific Ocean		
United States		Federal Waters		South Pacific Ocean		
United States		Federal Waters		Gulf of Alaska		
United States		Federal Waters		Caribbean Sea		

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
No GIS details available									